

Sub-Hour Timescale Behaviour Of The Solar Resource

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Abstract

The solar resource changes through a combination of deterministic variability due to the orbit and rotation of the Earth and stochastic intermittency induced by the Earth's atmosphere. The intermittency acts to complicate forecasts that could be made at the characteristic variability timescales. This report applies a novel method for quantifying measurement time series, that of Bayesian blocks, to the identification of characteristic timescales of the solar resource. It shows that the predictable few minute timescale variability of the solar resource is dominated by faster timescale intermittency, that only becomes fully resolved in 1 s pyranometer measurements for changes in global horizontal irradiance at the level of 50 W/m². The method can be used to identify times of day when intermittency is particularly prevalent, can be used to estimate the Linke turbidity factor for clear skies and can provide improved same day yield forecasts with only an hour of measurements taken directly after sunrise.

Keywords: intermittency, variability, solar, forecasting

1 INTRODUCTION

The Sun constitutes an inexpensive form of sustainable, yet highly variable, energy generation, for which there is an added need to cope with the intermittency in the derived energy arising from changeable environmental and operational conditions. Here variability will be defined as the longer timescale, low frequency, easily predictable changes in solar resource from the expected diurnal and seasonal changes given by the rotation of the Earth and its orbit around the Sun; whereas intermittency will be the more random fluctuations that are hard to predict in advance, such as weather related effects, cloud motion, electronic issues in the balance of system components, etc. Variability is obviously an issue when supply and demand requirements are out of phase, e.g. people need to power lights and heating when the Sun is out of view, but as those times are predictable they can generally be easily mitigated for through the use of an energy storage system (ESS), at least in the short term hour→days timescale. Ramp rates in changeable power output can still pose a challenge in terms of direct integration in to the electricity grid relative to how it currently operates [1, 2, 3], intermittency can further lead to random power outages or frequency deviations on the grid [4] that risk the reliability of energy supply in less predictable ways if not properly quantified in advance, or limiting the operational lifetime of an ESS [5, 6, 7]. Intermittency, by its rapid and random nature, leads to further issues in tracking changes in a resource, and the scheduling and dispatch of other resources to compensate for them. So the easy concept of an ESS to store up energy at times of excess to release again during times of deficit become complicated by the generally poorly quantified actual details of the time variability of the generation resource. Quantifying the variations solar resource therefore enables us to appropriately size an ESS and estimate the lifetime operation & maintenance (O&M) costs.

The solar resource variability on timescales down to the 1 h to 15 m scale are either highly predictable or have measurements readily available for further analysis [8, 9, 10], but many of the more random factors coming from the environment, surroundings, or the solar PV hardware have their own characteristic shorter cadence timescales that can be at the ≤minute scale [11, 12] and temporal averaging at the larger measured timescales can lead to unacceptable levels of bias when attempting modelling [12, 13]. It can also prove operationally expensive to underestimate changes in the solar resource, for example over-irradiance events from cloud reflection up to minutes in duration can blow fuses in utility scale PV systems [14], or errors in the simulated number of tap changes of up to ~ 70% are found when using 15 min solar values on a system operating on 30 s timescales [15]. So there are downstream O&M costs to consider, too, and these type of consideration can lead to recommendations to know the solar resource to minute timescales, but also suggestions that it may be necessary to monitor how it varies down to timescales in the region of 1 s–1 min are not uncommon either, e.g. [12, 15, 16]. There seem to be as many methods for quantifying solar irradiance intermittency as there are timescales to probe [17], but less in the way of general consensus as to which may be the most important to monitor at.

In the absence of large publicly available datasets, what is there to do in the way of establishing whether, if any, there are specific characteristic timescales in the solar resource that could aid in determining its effective modelling? CREST have a pyranometer on the rooftop of the Wolfson building that has been sampling the global horizontal irradiance (GHI), diffuse horizontal irradiance (DHI) and beam normal irradiance (BNI) at 1 s intervals for a number of years [13]. Fig. 1 shows GHI measurements from this pyranometer taken in 2018, with highlighted examples of clear sky, overcast and mixed clear/cloudy conditions as a percentage of the maximum GHI at local noon for their respective day representing how the solar resources varies compared to how we might expect it to. Each of the days shows both consistent variable and inconsistent intermittent behaviour that can result in irradiances both above and below those expected by modelled clear sky conditions. In the following sections I will detail in Section 2 a method of nonparametric analysis of time series data and how it can be applied to the Loughborough pyranometer dataset, with the results given in Section 3. Finally, I will discuss potential ways to exploit this information in terms of forecasting the solar resource and how to potentially smooth out the fluctuations in resource induced by intermittency in Section 4.

2 METHODOLOGY

In order to allow for comparisons to other sites, measurements of global horizontal irradiance (GHI) are used in this study, as taken by the Loughborough rooftop pyranometer at 1 s intervals (see, e.g. [13] for a description of the set up). Data gaps from missing readings can be tolerated by the method described in Section 2.1, but interpretation of results may become meaningless if the gap is too large, so any day is excluded from further analysis if it is missing data for periods of ≥ 1 h during daylight hours. This restriction leads to only 1 day (2018-12-15) being excluded from the 2018 dataset.

2.1 Bayesian Blocks

The method chosen in this study to detect and characterise variability in the time series of values is that of Bayesian blocks (BB) [18]; more specifically it is case 3 of [18] for interval based measurements with a known measurement error distribution. The intention of BB is to find the optimal segmentation of a data sequence of n independent measurements $x(t_n)$ such that consecutive periods with similar statistical properties are grouped together in to k blocks and the times of statistically significant variations in those properties are demarcated as change points (CP). The signal, $s(t)$, being measured in a sequence of times t_n , where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$, is the irradiance. The measurement at each time, $x_n \equiv x(t_n)$, is taken to be independent of the others, in that the errors of the measurement (σ) are statistically independent and so

$$x(t) = s(t) + z \quad (1)$$

where z is the measurement error and is known only through its statistical distribution. For simplicity, under the assumption of a normally distributed error with zero mean and identical measurement errors

$$P(z_n)dz_n = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{z_n}{\sigma}\right)^2\right] dz_n \quad (2)$$

taking a model signal as being approximately constant on sufficiently short timescales, $\delta s(\delta t) = s(t_2) - s(t_1) \rightarrow 0$ as $\delta t \rightarrow 0$, $\therefore s = \lambda$, then the likelihood of measurement n is

$$L_n = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x_n - \lambda}{\sigma}\right)^2\right] \quad (3)$$

and with independent measurements the block, k , likelihood as

$$L^{(k)} = \prod_n L_n = \frac{(2\pi)^{-\frac{N_k}{2}}}{\prod_n \sigma_n} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\sum_n \left(\frac{x_n - \lambda}{\sigma}\right)^2\right] \quad (4)$$

with the products and sum over those values of the index n that t is within the duration of block k . In reality the solar resource is constantly changing as the sun moves through the sky, so once the GHI has changed by a pre-selected significance level based on σ then the block duration $\delta t = CP_k - CP_{k-1}$ will define a characteristic timescale for solar resource variability. For regular changes in irradiance there will be regularly spaced block durations, for random changes there should be a more random distribution of δt . The number of change points (n_{cp}) in a day with intermittency is therefore also expected to be higher than in a day without it.

The optimal segmentation is that which maximises a fitness function with a Bayesian prior on the number of blocks penalising more complex models such that segmentation only occurs if it is sufficiently statistically significant (a conservative $p_0 = 0.01$ is used here). Again, under the assumption of a normally distributed error, the value of λ that maximises the block likelihood is

$$\lambda_{\max} = -\frac{b_k}{2a_k} \quad (5)$$

where

$$a_k = \frac{1}{2} \sum_n \frac{1}{\sigma^2}, \quad b_k = -\sum_n \frac{x_n}{\sigma^2}.$$

Inserting these in to equation 4 yields

$$\log L_{\max}^k = \frac{b_k^2}{4a_k} \quad (6)$$

as the fitness function to be used in the change point determination. Further details on the selection of threshold, σ , can be found in appendix A, but is in the range of $5 \leq \sigma \leq 50$ W/m² as appropriate in the following analyses.

2.2 Clearness Index

The dataset has been split according to whether the sky is *clear*, *overcast* or *mixed* so that any differences in characteristic timescales based on weather conditions can be investigated. The presence, or absence, of cloud in a day's dataset is determined using a version of the clearness index (CI) consistent with [19]:

$$CI = \frac{\text{daily insolation}}{\text{daily clear sky insolation}} \quad (7)$$

where the daily insolation is determined from the sum of pyranometer measurements and the clear sky insolation is determined from a model of what an ideal clear and dry atmosphere (cda) would be expected to give. The cda model used here is that of Ineichen & Perez [20] as implemented by the `pvl` Python package [21] at a Linke turbidity factor $T_L = 1$, which corresponds to the expected level of sunlight attenuation from a completely clear and dry atmosphere through an airmass=2. The `pvl` package is used throughout this study to model the expected, cloudless, clear sky behaviour at a range of turbidities: $T_L = 1$ is the ideal cda; the default turbidity factor

at Loughborough is expected to vary through the year and ranges from $2.95 \leq T_L \leq 4.4$ in the `pvl` library compiled from the SoDa 2003 database¹; for an industrialised smoggy area a level as high as $T_L = 7$ might be expected. The 2018 dataset is subdivided into conditions of *clear*, *mixed*, *overcast* according to

$$CI = \begin{cases} \text{clear,} & \text{if } CI > 0.85 \\ \text{mixed,} & \text{if } 0.2 < CI < 0.85 \\ \text{overcast,} & \text{if } CI < 0.2 \end{cases}$$

With the threshold values having been empirically determined from the 2018 data set following the arrow head plot scheme of [19].

2.3 Forecasting

Forecasting of the solar irradiance at ground level relies on having a clear sky model. The exact choice of clear sky model is generally less important than the available level of information to determine the optical path attenuation [22, 23], which in turn is mostly related to the airmass and the Linke turbidity. The turbidity of the atmosphere also changes the irradiance at ground and thus will further act to vary the expected number of change points and thus characteristic timescales and so this relation can be exploited to provide an estimate of T_L from the GHI measurements.

In `pvl` the default airmass model is that of Kasten & Young [24] and the clear sky follows Ineichen & Perez model with turbidity independent of airmass and requires only T_L as input. For fitting the clear sky model to PVGIS data the T_L is varied in steps of 0.1 and a best fit is found when the sum of square residuals (SSR) is minimised. For finding T_L with the BB a lookup table of the n_{cp} is generated for the measurement time period from a sequence of seven clear sky models with turbidity in the range $1 \leq T_L \leq 7$ calculated for that measurement day. A quadratic function of the form

$$T_L = an_{cp}^2 + bn_{cp} + c \quad (8)$$

was found to be the simplest to deal with the rapidly varying solar resource at large airmasses, but other forms may be equally valid at other times. The quadratic function is fit to these model values and the fit T_L^{fit} found for the measurement n_{cp}^{obs} . The fit result is bounded such that $T_L^{\text{fit}} < 0$ is noted and dropped from further analysis.

The irradiance forecast is evaluated against the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) [23]

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{N} \sum_t^N \left| \frac{\hat{G}_t - G_t}{G_t} \right| \quad (9)$$

where \hat{G}_t is the expected irradiance at time t , G_t is the measured irradiance. This will provide a measure of the accuracy of the measurement, but not whether there is an overall bias as to over- or under-estimate the value. It will also fail when $G_t = 0$, so measurement times are fixed to after sunrise and before sunset to mitigate this risk.

3 RESULTS & ANALYSIS

3.1 Irradiance

The CI results in a classification of 20 *clear* days, 305 *mixed* days, and 39 *overcast* days; though it should be noted that this classification is not a guarantee of ideal, cda model-like, behaviour on the *clear* days (see for example Fig. 15 for two days with identical CI, but very different intermittency behaviour) it provides the cleanest dataset for comparison to such conditions in a maritime climate that will have very few (if any) truly clear days. The default `pvl` T_L for the Loughborough area are found to systematically overestimate the T_L found from fitting PVGIS data for the *clear* days in the 2018 period (see appendix C for further details), thereby systematically underestimating the measured irradiance for those days. This demonstrates the necessity to find T_L from the Loughborough dataset (when possible) if we are to reliably estimate irradiance/insolation on a given day.

It is not just in the default T_L where we see some deviation between model and measurement. In Fig. 1 we see that generally for *mixed* weather days, but even on days classified as *clear* there are times when the GHI can exceed the expectation value for even an ideal cda when $T_L = 1$. In Fig. 2 the GHI values for 2018 are histogrammed and compared to `pvl` model atmosphere simulations for cda and default turbidity levels. As expected, the *overcast* days show a significant reduction in GHI compared to their clear sky expectation. However, although the simulated days never exceed a GHI of 1000 W/m^2 , the *clear* and *mixed* condition days have a statistically significant number of measurements for which the GHI exceeds that upper limit expectation value. Such levels of overirradiance due to cloud or albedo enhancement are not unheard of, highs of 1.9 suns in 1 s measurements having been observed at other locations [25], but they will affect estimates of PV energy yield and stress the balance of system equipment's lifetime if clipped. These overirradiance events amount to a relatively small fraction at $\leq 0.2\%$ of readings, but at 12.6 h that would still be equivalent to an extra winter day or two's worth of energy that would be clipped if sizing the inverter based on simulation expectation alone. These findings are consistent with earlier ones demonstrating that hourly averaged measurement data underestimates PV performance due to transient weather induced inverter clipping, thus impacting the level of currents and powers that need to be considered in inverter component sizing [12]. Overirradiance from cloud enhancement events up to the level of 4% of readings have been observed at other sites [26], impacting ramp rates at the few minute timescale.

Perhaps even more notable in terms of overirradiance is that for the diffuse component, also plotted in Fig. 2. There is an approximate agreement between model and measurement that increasing turbidity increases the level of DHI, but what is actually measured by the Loughborough pyranometer is again significantly beyond the model expectation. That the introduction of clouds can increase

¹<https://www.soda-pro.com/home>

Figure 1: How the solar global horizontal irradiance (GHI) changes seasonally (left) and diurnally (right) for three weather conditions in 2018. Blue triangles (\blacktriangledown) are for a *clear* day, green crosses (\times) for *mixed* clear/cloudy conditions and red squares (\blacksquare) for an *overcast* day, each day normalised to the GHI expected at noon for a completely clear and dry atmosphere for on that day. The shaded regions indicate the expected range of values between a cda ($T_L = 1$) and urban smog ($T_L = 7$) conditions. The cyan and gold dashed lines represent the peak GHI at local noon each day according to cda and default turbidity conditions respectively.

DHI, e.g. through the reflection of the solar beam, is something that the clear sky model would not be expected to get right, but this is also observed in the *clear* days and so the accuracy of the turbidity factor are called in to question. Increasing atmospheric turbidity increases the fraction of diffuse irradiance, so from the irradiance measurements we might expect that the Loughborough atmosphere to have greater turbidity than the model databases account for. However, when we fit independent GHI measurements from PVGIS for the *clear* sky days we find the opposite is actually the case, the `pvlib` T_L estimates are always higher than the PVGIS fits, at an average of 1.43 extra atmospheres of extinction and at worse 2.04 more atmospheres.

From the right hand plot of Fig. 1 we see that the T_L value has some impact on the expected shape of the GHI time profile. therefore on the rate of change of GHI. By examining the characteristic timing properties of the clear sky irradiance we may be able to extract some information as to its turbidity level, perhaps even in real time, and use that for forecasting insolation, at least for a short time in to the future.

Figure 2: Histogramming the GHI (top panels) and DHI (bottom panels) for 2018 data. *Left*: The expectation values for a clear and dry atmosphere `pvlib` model for the dates classified as *clear* (blue), *mixed* (green), or *overcast* (red). *Middle*: As for the left plots, but for the `pvlib` default atmosphere turbidity model on those dates. *Right*: As before, but for the Loughborough pyranometer readings.

3.2 Bayesian Blocks

In section 2.1 a method for determining periods of characteristic variability changes was described. The sensitivity of the BB method to features is dependent upon the threshold value set for a change to be determined as significant or not. The fundamental sensitivity limit will be the measurement errors of the instrument itself, for which the pyranometer readings during the night are used as a means of determining the level of instrument noise in the absence of a signal (after removing the hour before sunrise and the hour after sunset to ensure there should be no potential twilight bias). The standard deviation of the night time readings is found to be $\sigma_{\text{night}} = 1.39 \text{ W/m}^2$ in the GHI readings (1.36 in the DHI), with a mean of -3.7 W/m^2 . Because there are a very large number of measurements in the dataset ($> 30 \times 10^6$) it is reasonable to expect that there will still be statistical fluctuations due to measurement error to even a few standard deviations. It was determined that setting $\sigma \geq 5 \text{ W/m}^2$ should reduce change points introduced from measurement errors to negligible levels.

In the left panel of Fig. 3 are plotted the number of change points (n_{cp}) for $\sigma = 5 \text{ W/m}^2$ versus the CI. The shaded region demarcates the n_{cp} that would be expected if all the days were model clear sky days with default T_L . The *overcast* days have little variability/intermittency so trend to cluster at low n_{cp} ; *mixed* conditions are unsteady and so have a large spread in n_{cp} ; *clear* sky conditions tend to cluster once again, but outside the upper end of the expected n_{cp} range. It is obvious that this plot shares the characteristics of the variability index [19] in that n_{cp} alone can not definitively characterise the weather conditions of a day, but the

trend in behaviour between the three CI classification regions may still hint at some underlying characteristic progression between weather regimes.

Fig. 4 histograms the duration of the blocks. In the top panels we see the expectation when modelling the clear sky for each of the *clear/mixed/overcast* days show a consistent behaviour, with a sharp cutoff at a characteristic timescale that increases with increasing threshold. That there should be a characteristic timescale is no surprise as the available solar resource will vary deterministically with zenith angle and the Sun moves through the sky with a fixed speed. What we see in the actual measurements is showing a more complex picture though. There is a definite, albeit small, peak of BB durations matching the expected direct component characteristic variability timescales in the *clear* weather data set, but the timescales are dominated by much shorter timescale intermittency. This intermittency all but wipes out the characteristic variability timescale under mixed weather conditions, but also has a trend of an increasing characteristic timescale with increasing σ . At the level of $\sigma = 5 \text{ W/m}^2$ the peak is in the 1 s bin and so the intermittency timescale is not even resolved. Overcast conditions, where the beam component is expected to be negligible with respect to the diffuse, show a broad characteristic peak timescale that is somewhere between the intermittency and variability ones.

When plotting the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of these histograms in Fig. 5 the distinctive behaviour for the CI groupings are made even more apparent, with *clear* skies showing a hybrid behaviour between the model diurnal signature and the *mixed* cloudy sky's continuous intermittency. However, once conditions become *overcast* the intermittency profile does move back close to the characteristic timescales. From plotting the CDF as a function of threshold we are able to determine at which point the intermittency timescale is fully resolved. In the right hand plot of Fig. 3 we see the percentage fraction of BB durations contained within the pyranometer measurement 1 s resolution bin asymptotically falling until it effectively reaches zero at $\sigma = 50 \text{ W/m}^2$ for both the *clear* and *mixed* datasets (*overcast* conditions already being fully time resolved). There is then a compromise to be made between selecting a low threshold for BB analysis, necessary for times when the solar resource may not vary as much or peak as high (e.g. around noon, or on winter days), but being subject to having unresolved features; or a high threshold, which may only be valid for summer days that have sufficient solar resource to register even a characteristic clear sky timescale change, or potentially missing smaller fluctuations (e.g. thin cloud).

Figure 3: *Left panel*: Arrow head plot of number of change points (n_{cp}) versus clearness index (CI) for the Loughborough rooftop pyranometer measurements taken in 2018. Also highlighted are the *clear* (\blacktriangledown), *mixed* (\times) and *overcast* (\blacksquare) days as in Fig. 1. The dotted lines define the CI classification thresholds. The shaded region corresponds to the expected n_{cp} for the default range of T_L in `pvlib`. *Right panel*: Percentage of Bayesian blocks of ≤ 1 s duration as a function of the significance threshold (σ) value according to all *clear* skies (solid line, \blacktriangledown), *mixed* (dash-dot line, \times) and *overcast* (dotted line, \blacksquare) classification.

A further feature of a BB analysis is that it is not solely quantifying how variable a time series is, but the position of the change point informs as to when the time sequence has changed. Fig. 6 plots the expected variation in GHI for a *clear* day, where $\Delta GHI = GHI_{n=t+\delta t} - GHI_{n=t}$ as time t varies during the day, δt here is taken as 900 s (15 min), with the winter solstice representing the minimum variation we can expect during the year and summer solstice the maximum. Due to the nature of the changing irradiance as the Sun traverses the sky the expected n_{cp} in any period of a day changes depending on the time of day, with symmetric peaks in the early morning and late afternoon and the rate dropping off when the Sun reaches culmination at local noon. These n_{cp} will also vary seasonally, as the Sun culminates at different elevations, but should do so in a regular and predictable fashion, whereas intermittency will randomly increase n_{cp} , thus also changing the characteristic timescales from predictable values. If we compare the diurnal change in solar resource for clear sky conditions in Fig. 6 we expect to see that the maximum rate of change in resource in the early morning and late afternoon is out of phase with the time of maximum solar resource at local noon. When histogramming the times of the 2018 dataset CP in Fig. 7 in 1 h and 15 min binning we see in the top panel simulations the expected behaviour of increasing from sunrise to a peak in mid-morning, dropping off around noon, increasing again through mid-afternoon, then dropping at sunset to be a good match to this expected behaviour. However, from the pyranometer measurement analysis in the lower panels what is actually happening is very different to expectation. Where the *mixed* and *overcast* conditions should be showing very low levels of variability in the solar resource at noon those days are in fact dominated by the fluctuations at that time. Again, probably not surprising, since at time of peak resource it takes the smallest of inputs to induce a significant enough change to be registered. *Clear* sky days once again show a hybrid behaviour, with the expected morning and afternoon peaks and a dip at noon (though not as pronounced as expected), but there is an additional cause of unsteady behaviour in the hour long binning showing up around 10 am. At the even shorter timescales of 15 min binning the picture starts to become even more complicated with multiple peaks and troughs in resource variability showing up through

Figure 4: Histograms of the Bayesian block durations. Blue shading denotes the *clear* sky data set, green the *mixed* conditions, red the *overcast*. Left panels are for $\sigma = 5 \text{ W/m}^2$ in the BB analysis, right panels are for $\sigma = 50 \text{ W/m}^2$. Top panels are the expectation from pvlib clear sky models, bottom panels are the Loughborough pyranometer 2018 measurements.

Figure 5: Cumulative distribution functions (cdf) for the Bayesian block duration histograms as a function of analysis threshold $5 \leq \sigma \leq 75 \text{ W/m}^2$. Divided according to weather classification: *clear* (left, solid lines), *mixed* (middle, dot-dashed lines), *overcast* (right, dotted lines). Model clear and dry atmosphere expectation denoted by dashed line. Line colours vary according to the analysis threshold as given in the legend.

the day. This could have implications to solar panel array configuration – if this variation in resource is due to local shading then a more reliable output may be gained facing West in the afternoon than facing East in the morning. However, at an alternative site in a more monsoon climate, for example, where cloud is expected to build up in the afternoon, the opposite may be true. This indicates how a BB analysis on local archival data could prove beneficial for resource maximisation.

Figure 6: How the solar resource changes diurnally. *Left*, the expected change in GHI in periods of 900s; *right*, the number of change points a Bayesian blocks analysis should detect. The dotted and dashed lines marking the expectation for changes of 5 and 9.8 W/m² respectively. The orange shaded zone delimits the range for the summer solstice, blue for the winter solstice. The red lines and grey shaded area delimit the regions where no change point is expected to be detectable due to being below the threshold of significance.

Figure 7: Histogram of the number of change points as a function of time of day. Shading denotes the clear (blue) sky, mixed (green), overcast (red) conditions. Histograms have been normalised to compensate for the different number of days in each classification dataset. *Top panels*: expectation from pvlib clear sky model. *Bottom panels*: Loughborough pyranometer 2018 measurements. *Left panels*: 1 h binning. *Right panels*: 15 min binning. The midnight CP peak is an artefact, because the first data point of the day is also the first change point (by definition).

4 DISCUSSION

We have seen that the measured GHI often exceeds the model expectation, but does so in a way that would seem to require a higher than expected turbidity to match the DHI behaviour. Not only would increasing the T_L contradict basic physics here, the more extinction the lower the expected irradiance after all, but it would also contradict the results of fitting PVGIS measurements for the 2018 dataset clear sky days where the T_L is calculated to be on average 1.43 lower than the pvlib default library value for those days (details in appendix C). The overirradiance can be understood in terms of cloud enhancement effects (e.g. [26, 16, 14]) which would not be

accounted for in a clear sky model, but in order to be able to make accurate advance estimates of PV yield even for actually clear skies will require a better estimate of T_L to be successful.

4.1 Linke Turbidity Factor Calculation

We see from the shaded regions in Fig. 1 how the T_L value changes the shape of the time profile of the GHI. As BB are a sensitive tool for measuring changes in a time sequence, can they also be used as a tool for determining the T_L on a given day? In Fig. 8 the pyranometer measurements for the maximum CI day in the *clear* data set, along with PVGIS measurements for that same day, which are consistent with the pyranometer values, albeit on a 1 h timescale. The default expectation value for T_L in *pvl*ib based on a measurement from 2003 would be $T_L = 3.97$, the best fit to the PVGIS measurements show the atmosphere on that day in 2018 to be substantially clearer at $T_L = 2.2$. Generating a lookup table of the number of expected change points for clear sky models in the range $1 \leq T_L \leq 7$ and comparing those to the measurement n_{cp}^{obs} gives a fit of $T_L = 2.08$. This BB based measurement is consistent with the PVGIS measurement and as we see in Table 1 both are significant improvements to most library values for T_L for the Loughborough area. This is not to say a library value is not useful, conditions on average will trend to be less than clear sky and so in aggregate a higher T_L would better predict the averaged long term yield, even if on a given single clear day it would consistently bias it to be an underestimate. Extending the analysis to all of the 2018 *clear* days shows only 7 out of the 20 days result in an improved T_L derived from the n_{cp} , the remainder resulting in wildly inaccurate, or even unphysical, estimates. This is due to the fundamental nature of fitting to an ill-posed problem: there is not a unique solution to the n_{cp} fit. A clearer sky achieving higher GHI from a low T_L results in more change points from the increased irradiance; but a sky with more intermittency from cloud/enhanced aerosol content is also dominated by shorter timescale fluctuations that introduce more change points. We see this in the residuals of Fig. 8 where the intermittency around noon is particularly noticeable. Collecting a library of the clearest days from an archive dataset could eventually result in having a more relevant library of T_L values for a given location, but just because a day has a particular T_L value in one year does not automatically mean it will have the same T_L in another and some times of year are more likely to encounter clear conditions than others so it could take a long time to build up sufficient statistics. Fits to PVGIS measurements will provide a more accurate T_L , as indeed will fitting the pyranometer GHI measurements directly, but these come after the fact, when one already has the actual energy yield numbers to hand. Is there some means to improve the forecast of that yield in advance, even if only on the same day?

Figure 8: The GHI values for 2018-05-14. *Left panel*: The Loughborough pyranometer measurements are given by the yellow \blacktriangledown , PVGIS readings by the black $*$; the light/dark grey shaded areas show the *pvl*ib clear sky model expectation for $1 \leq T_L \leq 7$ and $2.95 \leq T_L \leq 4.4$ respectively; the lines are for T_L values from various sources: green solid line from the BB fit for $\sigma = 50 \text{ W/m}^2$, black dashed line a fit to PVGIS points, the cyan dotted line the default *pvl*ib database value, the orange dash-dot line from the Meteororm database, the red dash-dot-dot line from Aeronet values. *Right panel* contains the residuals to the pyranometer readings markers and colours as given in the figure legend, the dark/light shaded regions bound $\sigma = \pm 5, 50 \text{ W/m}^2$ respectively.

Table 1: Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) to the T_L values for 2018-05-14

Source	T_L	MAPE [%]
BB	2.08	2.87
PVGIS	2.2	2.91
Meteororm	3.56	12.96
Aeronet	3.95	16.09
<i>pvl</i> ib	3.97	16.25

Table 2: The mean and standard deviation to the residual (measured – modelled) GHI insolation for the 20 CI identified *clear* sky days in the 2018 Loughborough pyranometer data.

scenario	mean [kWh/m ² /day]	std [kWh/m ² /day]
cda	-0.897	0.291
default	0.534	0.189
1h	-0.259	0.641
2h	-0.078	0.947
3h	-0.031	2.125

4.2 Forecasting

The further in to a day the time series goes, the more likely it is to contain some level of intermittency that would bias a BB n_{cp} fit, but we have already seen in Fig. 7 that the effects of intermittency peaks at noon, whereas Fig. 6 shows the rate of n_{cp} for a clear sky should reach a maximum earlier in the day. Would making a forecast based on a T_L fit from the measurements taken prior to noon result in a better estimate of the day's yield? In Table 2 the residuals of the modelled from the measured GHI insolation are

calculated and the mean and standard deviation for the 20 *clear* days are taken. In Fig. 7 we see that there is an additional external influence around 10am that could bias the derived n_{cp} so here only the first 3 h after sunrise are examined, increasing in hour long steps. These results are compared to the expectation for the default clear sky model and to an ideal cda. As expected, we see that the cda greatly overestimates the yield, because the sky is never that clear; we also see that the default clear sky models underestimate the yield from the aforementioned tendency to overestimate the T_L . As we increase the number of measurement points with increasing time from sunrise we see from the means that the overall bias improves, though also tending to an overestimate of irradiance, but the standard deviation gets increasingly wide. This is expected behaviour, intermittency only inflates the n_{cp} leading to a tendency to underestimate T_L and thus overestimate GHI . Intermittency is not always present at the same time, so for 15 out of the 20 *clear* days it does not significantly bias the early morning estimates, leading to improved averages, but for the remaining 5 days it yields such unrealistic results it seriously impacts the spread of values. Fig. 9 contrasts two neighbouring days attributed identical CI: 2018-08-02 shows relatively little intermittency and is thus a good candidate for fitting T_L and provides an accurate yield forecast; 2018-07-03 has significant intermittency, the CI matches the previous day only because the overirradiance compensates for the shadowing losses, and is thus a poor day for a forecast from an n_{cp} based T_L fit. So in summary, in the long run while the aggregate yield may likely be improved, there is no guarantee of an accurate estimate for any individual day.

Figure 9: *Top panels*: residuals of GHI (measured - fit) for PVGIS (*), Loughborough pyranometer (●), the shaded regions delimit blue $\sigma = 5$, shaded red $\sigma = 50$ W/m^2 . *Bottom panels*: The number of change points in an hour as a function of hour from sunrise, the expectation values bounded by the dash-dotted lines and shaded blue for the range $1 \leq T_L \leq 7$. *left panels* are for 2018-07-02, *right panels* are for 2018-07-03.

That we do see an improvement in accuracy even in the first hour of the day is encouraging and from Fig. 3 we know that many days show low levels of intermittency, so it is interesting to see if a general improvement in resource forecast can be achieved across the full dataset. In Fig. 10 the MAPE from the default `pvl` clear sky model T_L is plotted against the MAPE for a T_L derived from the n_{cp} calculated in the first hour of measurements taken after sunrise and assuming that represents the clear sky T_L for the entire day. Early morning intermittency in the first hour makes a physically viable estimate impossible for 24% of days, but of the remainder 68% of those showed a reduction in GHI error. At low MAPE there is general agreement between the two, the most notable improvement being for default `pvl` days with the highest MAPE that are likely to be overcast days rather than highly intermittent mixed condition ones. Although the situation does improve again once the period of intermittency has passed. This simplistic method of forecasting will not match the levels of accuracy or precision that more complex nowcasting methods, that update during the day as conditions change, can achieve (e.g. [27]), but as a first means of improving upon long term forecast estimates with up to date conditions it shows promise for further investigation. Introducing machine learning methods that can incorporate additional information regarding the likelihood of intermittency impacting the n_{cp} could be a particularly interesting area for future research.

Temporal averaging of the datapoints could smooth out the extremities of the intermittency, but at the potential cost of also smoothing out the characteristic timescales needed for the n_{cp} calculation without appropriate selection of the averaging time period. The intermittency in the point-like pyranometer measurements will also become less prominent when spatially averaged, since each cell of a PV module, or modules of an array, or arrays in different farms, can be subject to different shadowing effects [28]. On a large enough scale this is what the grid does to limit the impacts of intermittency, but even though pyranometer measurements do have the largest variance, on a household or even SME scale there can still be significant levels of power output fluctuation [29]. Even utility scale facilities are not immune to consequences that large overirradiance events, that correlate with periods of high intermittency, can bring [14]. As intermittency can never be entirely removed it must instead be mitigated for [30], at least up to the deterministic variability timescales where it can be more reliably modelled for.

Figure 10: The Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) from the default `pvlib` clear sky model for a day versus the equivalent clear sky model with T_L calculated from fitting the n_{cp} in the first hour after sunrise for the 2018 Loughborough data. The dotted line is a 1:1 to guide the eye and not a fit.

4.3 Mitigation

The use of energy storage not only smoothes the intermittency, but can also compensate for the time shift between energy generation and energy demand

- Supercapacitors are a capable means to smooth output [30], certainly to beyond the unresolved ≤ 1 s timescale, and able to cope with the frequent charge/discharge cycles that such short duration fluctuations would demand, but would probably only be a means to bridge the gap to the longer timescale stability that the user demands.
- Batteries are the generally most favoured solution, but intermittency will stress the charge/discharge cycle ultimately impacting the battery lifetime and proving an expensive item to replace [6] and require deterministic management rules that may not always play well with the stochastic aspect of the solar resource [30].
- Flywheels [31] have a large upfront cost, but then are generally a long lived and reliable storage solution when it comes to being used many times a day, but still need consideration as to the wear and tear introduced if quickly and irregularly swapping between charge/discharge states.
- Pumped hydro could take the irregular supply of input energy into a large gravitational inertial storage reservoir, provided there is the space and suitable geography to contain it, but would still likely only meet the offset between supply and demand for a few hours.
- A compressed gas energy storage medium seems a more suitable medium if desiring to shift between summer maximum solar generation and winter maximum energy demand, either through CAES or hydrogen generation, but once again an intermittent supply of energy proves detrimental to maintaining the regular pressures needed for efficient production/storage of the gas [32].

What is really needed to cope with solar intermittency is a means of inertia to ride through the intermittent periods, so investigating alternative means of building inertia into solar energy might result in an appropriate solution. Apart from mass-momentum or gravity then thermal storage, through the heating of a material, also provides a means of inertia. Thermal energy can be generated, either through solar concentration or DC heating, then be converted into useful electricity via Stirling engine and also be an option for combined heat and power industrial processes or domestic heating. The process will never be as efficient as directly injecting solar PV generated electricity into the grid, but in terms of reliability in predicting the energy flow, reducing stress on external components and their associated O&M costs, and flexibility in terms of when it can be used then the pros of compromising on efficiency may in some situations outweigh the cons.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The deterministic variability of the solar resource has a characteristic timescale that is an order of magnitude or two slower than the stochastic intermittency timescales that complicate the large scale adoption of solar energy. Intermittency is always present at some level, even in clear sky conditions, and this will act to make yield forecasting difficult. Intermittency is only fully resolved in these 1 s pyranometer measurements for changes in $GHI \geq 50$ W/m^2 . A Bayesian blocks analysis of the measurement time series is a really sensitive means to detect periods dominated by intermittency. If intermittency is low, BB can secondarily be used to then estimate the Linke turbidity factor, which in turn can be used to improve resource forecasts for energy yield estimation.

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References

- [1] R. Fares, “Renewable Energy Intermittency Explained: Challenges, Solutions, and Opportunities - Scientific American Blog Network,” 2015.
- [2] M. A. Eltawil and Z. Zhao, “Grid-connected photovoltaic power systems: Technical and potential problems—A review,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 14, pp. 112–129, 1 2010.
- [3] G. C. Wang, J. Luis Bosch, B. Kurtz, I. D. L. Parra, E. Wu, and J. Kleissl, “Worst Expected Ramp Rates from Cloud Speed Measurements,” *Conference Record of the IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference*, pp. 2281–2286, 6 2019.
- [4] M. A. Syed and M. Khalid, “Machine Learning Based Controlled Filtering for Solar PV Variability Reduction with BESS,” *2021 International Conference on Sustainable Energy and Future Electric Transportation, SeFet 2021*, 1 2021.
- [5] B. Zohuri and P. McDaniel, “Energy storage technologies and their role in renewable integration,” *Introduction to Energy Essentials*, pp. 277–320, 1 2021.
- [6] A. J. Crawford, Q. Huang, M. C. Kintner-Meyer, J. G. Zhang, D. M. Reed, V. L. Sprenkle, V. V. Viswanathan, and D. Choi, “Lifecycle comparison of selected Li-ion battery chemistries under grid and electric vehicle duty cycle combinations,” *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 380, pp. 185–193, 3 2018.
- [7] K. Moy, S. B. Lee, S. Harris, and S. Onori, “Design and validation of synthetic duty cycles for grid energy storage dispatch using lithium-ion batteries,” *Advances in Applied Energy*, vol. 4, p. 100065, 11 2021.
- [8] T. Tomson, V. Russak, and A. Kallis, “Dynamic Behavior of Solar Radiation,” *Modeling Solar Radiation at the Earth’s Surface: Recent Advances*, pp. 257–281, 2008.
- [9] T. Huld, R. Müller, and A. Gambardella, “A new solar radiation database for estimating pv performance in europe and africa,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 86, no. 6, pp. 1803–1815, 2012.
- [10] System Operator for Northern Ireland, “<https://www.soni.ltd.uk/media/documents/system-data-qtr-hourly-2022-2023.xlsx>.”
- [11] G. Vijayakumar, M. Kummert, S. A. Klein, and W. A. Beckman, “Analysis of short-term solar radiation data,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 79, pp. 495–504, 11 2005.
- [12] S. Ransome and P. Funtan, “Why hourly averaged measurement data is insufficient to model pv system performance accurately,” in *Proc. of the 20th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference, PVSEC*, pp. 2752–2755, WIP-Renewable Energies, 2005.
- [13] K. Gibson, I. R. Cole, B. Goss, T. R. Betts, and R. Gottschalg, “Compensation of temporal averaging bias in solar irradiance data,” *IET Renewable Power Generation*, vol. 11, no. 10, pp. 1288–1294, 2017.
- [14] L. R. do Nascimento, T. de Souza Viana, R. A. Campos, and R. Rütther, “Extreme solar overirradiance events: Occurrence and impacts on utility-scale photovoltaic power plants in brazil,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 186, pp. 370–381, 2019.
- [15] M. Lave, M. J. Reno, and R. J. Broderick, “Characterizing local high-frequency solar variability and its impact to distribution studies,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 118, pp. 327–337, 2015.
- [16] G. M. Lohmann and A. H. Monahan, “Effects of temporal averaging on short-term irradiance variability under mixed sky conditions,” *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 3131–3144, 2018.
- [17] R. Blaga and M. Paulescu, “Quantifiers for the solar irradiance variability: A new perspective,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 174, pp. 606–616, 2018.
- [18] J. D. Scargle, J. P. Norris, B. Jackson, and J. Chiang, “Studies in Astronomical Time Series Analysis. VI. Bayesian Block Representations,” *Astrophysical Journal*, vol. 764, p. 167, Feb. 2013.
- [19] S. Stein, Joshua, C. W. Hansen, and J. Reno, Matthew, “The variability index: a new and novel metric for quantifying irradiance and pv output variability,” Tech. Rep. SAND2012-2088C, Sandia National Labs, 2012.
- [20] P. Ineichen and R. Perez, “A new airmass independent formulation for the linke turbidity coefficient,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 73, no. 3, pp. 151–157, 2002.
- [21] W. F. Holmgren, C. W. Hansen, and M. A. Mikofski, “pvlib python: a python package for modeling solar energy systems,” *Journal of Open Source Software*, vol. 3, no. 29, p. 884, 2018.
- [22] F. Antonanzas-Torres, R. Urraca, J. Polo, O. Perpiñán-Lamigueiro, and R. Escobar, “Clear sky solar irradiance models: A review of seventy models,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 107, pp. 374–387, 2019.
- [23] R. H. Inman, H. T. Pedro, and C. F. Coimbra, “Solar forecasting methods for renewable energy integration,” *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 535–576, 2013.
- [24] F. Kasten and A. T. Young, “Revised optical air mass tables and approximation formula,” *Applied Optics*, vol. 28, pp. 4735–4738, Nov. 1989.
- [25] C. A. Gueymard, “Cloud and albedo enhancement impacts on solar irradiance using high-frequency measurements from thermopile and photodiode radiometers. part 1: Impacts on global horizontal irradiance,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 153, pp. 755–765, 2017.
- [26] R. H. Inman, Y. Chu, and C. F. Coimbra, “Cloud enhancement of global horizontal irradiance in california and hawaii,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 130, pp. 128–138, 2016.
- [27] M. Paulescu and E. Paulescu, “Short-term forecasting of solar irradiance,” *Renewable Energy*, vol. 143, pp. 985–994, 2019.
- [28] J. Marcos, L. Marroyo, E. Lorenzo, D. Alvira, and E. Izco, “Power output fluctuations in large scale pv plants: One year observations with one second resolution and a derived analytic model,” *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 218–227, 2011.
- [29] F. P. Kreuwel, W. H. Knap, L. R. Visser, W. G. van Sark, J. Vilà-Guerau de Arellano, and C. C. van Heerwaarden, “Analysis of high frequency photovoltaic solar energy fluctuations,” *Solar Energy*, vol. 206, pp. 381–389, 2020.
- [30] S. Shivashankar, S. Mekhilef, H. Mokhlis, and M. Karimi, “Mitigating methods of power fluctuation of photovoltaic (pv) sources – a review,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 59, pp. 1170–1184, 2016.
- [31] M. E. Amiryar and K. R. Pullen, “A review of flywheel energy storage system technologies and their applications,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 7, no. 3, 2017.
- [32] T. Egeland-Eriksen, A. Hajizadeh, and S. Sartori, “Hydrogen-based systems for integration of renewable energy in power systems: Achievements and perspectives,” *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 46, no. 63, pp. 31963–31983, 2021.

A DETERMINATION OF THRESHOLD

A.1 Measurement Uncertainty

To determine the measurement errors the pyranometer readings during the night are used as a means of determining the level of pure instrument noise in the absence of a signal (after removing the hour before sunrise and the hour after sunset to ensure there should be no potential twilight bias). Under the assumption the instrument measurement errors should be normally distributed in the absence of a signal, the statistical properties are given in Table 3. The standard deviation of the night time readings is found to be consistent between the GHI readings and DHI readings, though note that the night time measurements do indicate a negative offset, or bias, to the readings. Although this mean value is physically meaningless, it does show the potential for systematic bias in the determined irradiance values. Provided the bias is a constant offset and not correlated with some other local parameter (i.e. temperature) then it will not affect the BB algorithm's calculation of CP and can be safely ignored. As a pyranometer is making a temperature measurement rather than light level measurement per se, then the most obvious source of a systematic bias would be temperature related, particularly at night when the ambient temperature will be lower. To test this hypothesis, as shown in Fig. 11 the ambient temperature measurement for each night time irradiance measurement is plotted, for which a Pearson correlation co-efficient of $-0.167(-0.211)$ for GHI(DHI) respectively. This does not indicate any significant evidence of correlation of night time measurement with ambient temperature and what little correlation there may be would seem to go in the opposite direction than expected. A run sequence may indicate a tendency for the measurement bias to be stronger in the summer months and lower in the winter ones. Clearer skies in the summer could allow for colder sky blackbody temperatures to be a potential influence on the readings, but there is no supporting evidence as to the presence, or amount, of cloud to test such an hypothesis.

Cross-checking the night time analysis with daytime measurement in the presence of a signal is complicated by the fact that there is a very strong diurnal variation in the solar resource from the changing airmass the sunlight has to travel through as the solar elevation angle changes through the day; and there is a random influence of cloud to also contend with. The relative change is least as the Sun reaches culmination at local noon, so a time interval of ± 1 hour around local noon was taken to be a good period to perform a test in, with a clear day containing no evidence for cloud influence during that time identified as 2018-06-26. The statistical distribution of the measurements in that 2 h period are also given in Table 3. The values for the standard deviation are higher, as expected given the solar resource will still not be entirely constant in all that time period, but are consistent with the night time measurements.

Figure 11: Night time measurements from the Loughborough rooftop pyranometer. **Top left:** the GHI and DHI readings for each night in 2018, excluding the hour before sunrise and hour after sunset. **Top right:** histogram of the GHI and DHI night time readings. **Bottom left:** the ambient temperature readings for the same time periods. **Bottom right:** the ambient temperature readings versus the equivalent pyranometer GHI/DHI readings.

Figure 12: Loughborough pyranometer readings (blue) and `pvlib` simulations (yellow) for 2018-06-26. Left panels are for GHI, right panels for DHI. Top panels are the readings; middle panels are pyranometer-model residual values as a function of time; lower panels are the residual values histogrammed. The readings ± 1 hour from noon are highlighted by the green shaded areas.

Table 3: Estimating the Loughborough pyranometer measurement error uncertainty by two different methods: i) from the statistical distribution of measurements taken at night to represent the absence of a measurement signal; ii) from the distribution of measurements taken within ± 1 h of solar noon to represent measurements with maximal signal, but the time of least change in solar resource due to diurnal motion.

residuals measured-modelled	mean [W/m ²]	σ [W/m ²]
GHI (night)	-3.70	1.39
GHI (noon)	79.95	2.37
DHI (night)	3.46	1.36
DHI (noon)	-90.23	1.15

A.2 Change Point Threshold

The histogram of the entire year's worth of night time measurements, amounting to 12,765,011 readings, is shown in Fig. 13 and compared to a random sample of the same number of points generated from a normal distribution with the same mean and standard deviation. The measurement points are slightly more tightly grouped than the normal distribution would lead us to expect, but that could in part be related to the measurements being integer and so truncated with respect to the floating point random numbers. The measurements would also appear to be not entirely symmetric, again indicating that the measurement uncertainty may not be entirely Gaussian, but this would seem to relate mostly to a small number of outlier events. From this it was determined that a conservative $\sigma \geq 5 \text{ W/m}^2$ should result in a negligible contribution of the instrument measurement error in the determination of CP for the daytime readings.

Figure 13: Histogram of the pyranometer night time readings, GHI/DHI in blue/yellow respectively. A histogram of a normal distribution with the GHI mean and standard deviation is also plotted in green. Reference lines in red are: mean (solid line), mean \pm standard deviation (dotted), mean $\pm 5 \text{ W/m}^2$ (dashed).

Thankfully, once above the measurement threshold the BB method should be relatively insensitive to the choice of σ [18] Fig. 14 shows the tight correlation, Pearson correlation coefficient $\rho = 0.99$, between the n_{cp} for $\sigma = 5 \text{ W/m}^2$ and $\sigma = 50 \text{ W/m}^2$ BB analyses. The number n_{cp} will inevitably fall when increasing σ , so a suitable threshold needs to be chosen based on the compromise between sensitivity to small features and the available amount of measurements in a time period, as seen in Fig. 15 when calculating the n_{cp} in hour long periods on individual days with different levels of intermittency. A single value of $\sigma = 25 \text{ W/m}^2$ is probably a good compromise between removing low level intermittency that is not sensitive to changes in the levels of aerosol content on a *clear* day (2018-07-02), but is to when those aerosols form into the presence of small amounts of cloud (2018-07-03). Alternatively the tests could be repeated at minimum and maximum threshold levels to test for consistency in results when looking for the absolute clearest of sky conditions.

Figure 14: The number of change points n_{cp} when the threshold for a significance threshold $\sigma = 5 \text{ W/m}^2$ versus the number for $\sigma = 50 \text{ W/m}^2$. Plotted are the Loughborough pyranometer measurements for all weather conditions and the expected values from `pvlib` simulations for clear sky conditions.

Figure 15: The number of change points in an hour as a function of hour from sunrise. Expectation values by the dash-dotted lines and shaded area for $1 \leq \text{Linke turbidity factor} \leq 7$. left: 2018-07-02 right: 2018-07-03 top: GHI values middle: $\sigma = 5$ bottom: $\sigma = 50$

B BAYESIAN BLOCKS REPRESENTATION

Bayesian blocks [18] segments data according to periods of similar statistical properties, dividing those regions at *change points* where the statistical properties change according to some pre-defined significance threshold. The (number of blocks) is the (number of change points - 1) and the first change point is always fixed at the time of the first measurement. Though the algorithm is not always the most sensitive determinant of variability in terms of returning a significance, it does provide extra information over, for example, a straightforward variability index (see appendix E): the Bayesian blocks algorithm allows us to determine the time of when variability is observed; the block duration will give us a characteristic timescale the statistical properties are consistent over; the mean irradiance for the block can also be returned by the algorithm to give an estimate of flux level.

As an example, in Fig. 16 we see the calculated blocks for changes in statistical properties for $\sigma = 5 \text{ W/m}^2$ at a significance level of $p_0 = 0.01$ for Loughborough pyranometer GHI measurements taken on 2018-06-26 and zoomed in to three time periods exhibiting behaviour of interest. The day consists of 86400 measurements taken at one second intervals and which 398 change points are identified at that threshold. Around sunrise we see that the measurements transition from negative values to the positive signal, the block calculation unaffected by the offset this negative bias induces. Around 6am there is a long duration excursion from the expected irradiance curve, and at close to 10:40 there is a very short timescale feature, both clearly identified by the block change points and the block duration showing the change in characteristic timescale an expected ramp rate would take. Also plotted are a `pvlib` default clear sky model simulation for the same day, for which the day is divided by 370 change points of more even durations.

Figure 16: Bayesian blocks fits (red solid lines) to the Loughborough pyranometer 2018-06-26 measurements (left panels, blue crosses) and `pvlib` simulations (right panels, crosses). The block edges define the change points. Top panel is the full day, the lower panels are zoomed in to specific features on the day.

C TURBIDITY

The turbidity of the atmosphere determines the amount of extrasolar radiation that reaches the ground to be available for PV conversion. It is affected by many sources, such as airmass, amount of water vapour, gas concentrations (i.e. ozone levels), amount of aerosols, etc. The Linke turbidity factor (T_L) is a means of simplifying this such that a reference clear and dry atmosphere at an airmass of 2 is defined as $T_L = 1$ and the turbidity level is referenced to the number of these atmospheres required to match the observed level of attenuation of solar radiation. In `pvlib` there is a default library of climatological turbidity values for the globe, such that clear sky irradiance values can be queried based on location and interpolated to the day of interest. For Loughborough these values range $2.95 \leq T_L \leq 4.4$, but are based on measurements taken in 2003 and we can use the determined clear sky GHI readings to determine how well they match to the 2018 dataset. In Fig. 17 we see that the residuals between the measurements made on 2018-06-26 and the interpolated model show the model to be a poor fit, greatly underestimating the clear sky irradiance on this day. PVGIS measurements taken for the same day show a good match to the Loughborough readings and a fit can be made by varying the T_L in the `pvlib` model and minimising $\sum(GHI_{pvgis} - GHI_{pvlib})^2$. Also shown for reference are the T_L from the `Meteonorm`² package, which provides both its own database of T_L and those for the nearest Aeronet³ station to the location (here about 100 miles from Loughborough) also available in the `Meteonorm` package.

Fig. 18 contains the PVGIS fit T_L for each of the *clear* days in comparison to the T_L for `pvlib`, `Meteonorm` and Aeronet databases. As can be seen the historical database T_L values are a poor match for the fits to the actual clear sky irradiation values for 2018, generally underestimating the clarity of the sky, thus demonstrating the need for valid on-the-day measurements of T_L when it comes to forecasting or estimating PV yields.

Figure 17: An example of clear sky turbidity for 2018-06-26. The upper panel shows the GHI values. The pyranometer measured GHI values are given by the yellow circles, the PVGIS readings by the black stars. The light grey shaded areas show the `pvlib` clearsky model ranges between Linke turbidities of 1 (clear and dry sky) and 7 (urban smog) and dark grey the default library expected range of 2.95 to 4.4 for Loughborough's coordinates respectively. The lower panel are the residuals of readings - `pvlib` model estimation for various Linke turbidities and their sources as given in the figure legend.

²<https://meteonorm.com/en/>

³<https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

Figure 18: Linke turbidity values. The `pvlib` database is marked by grey for both the stored monthly values for the Loughborough area and their interpolation; in yellow the Meteonorm; in red the nearest Aeronet station. The fits to PVGIS for the 2018 Loughborough *clear* days are shown by the blue stars.

In Table 4 the mean average percentage error (MAPE) is calculated based on the relevant package default T_L or the best fit values to GHI measurements taken on the *clear* days identified in the Loughborough pyranometer 2018 data. The BB fits are performed at a significance threshold $\sigma = 25 \text{ W/m}^2$ and $p_0 = 0.01$ for measurements from the full day and sub-divided in to the periods 1,2,3 hours after sunrise. Measurement periods for which there is a lot of intermittency will tend to result in $T_L < 1$ and often negative (i.e. unphysical) values that can be easily identified as not clear sky conditions on this basis, with prior identification of a suitable analysis threshold (see appendix A).

Table 4: The mean average percentage error for the GHI modelled for either the library or best fit T_L value for the *clear* days in 2018.

Date	pvlib		PVGIS		Meteonet		Aeronet		n_{cp}	day		1h		2h		3h	
	T_L	MAPE	T_L	MAPE	T_L	MAPE	T_L	MAPE		T_L	MAPE	T_L	MAPE	T_L	MAPE	T_L	MAPE
2018-02-25	3.56	18.61	1.9	4.51	2.98	12.1	2.72	8.93	250	1.5	8.43	1.69	6.16	1.96	4.19	1.5	8.43
2018-04-05	3.48	18.94	2.1	18.96	3.55	19.05	3.99	20.03	561	-0.03	49.78	1.52	21.82	1.94	19.26	2.45	18.52
2018-05-05	3.79	10.7	2.7	5.59	3.56	8.77	3.95	12	816	-3.53	146	2.09	10.14	3.04	5.6	3.64	9.42
2018-05-06	3.81	11.85	2.3	3.66	3.56	9.63	3.95	13.01	431	-0.01	35.66	2.09	5.51	2.99	4.3	2.54	2.41
2018-05-14	3.97	16.25	2.2	2.91	3.56	12.96	3.95	16.09	456	0.25	24.31	1.45	8.01	1.47	7.77	1.96	3.28
2018-05-15	3.99	20.34	2.7	23.97	3.56	20.32	3.95	20.31	712	-4.52	388	2.09	32.69	1.96	35.08	2.93	21.93
2018-05-20	4	11.7	2.6	14.25	3.56	10.6	3.95	1.55	617	-3.67	247	2.92	11.31	2.87	11.66	2.99	10.88
2018-06-22	4.09	17.1	2.1	6.92	3.42	11.78	3.64	13.58	494	-1.14	59.48	1.4	14.04	1.83	9.07	1.96	7.91
2018-06-25	4.13	14.59	2.2	10.08	3.42	6.7	3.64	8.94	416	3.56	10.73	1.4	14.38	1.83	9.56	1.96	8.44
2018-06-26	4.14	15.92	2.1	5.36	3.42	9.82	3.64	11.68	398	2.47	4.39	4.08	15.39	4.25	16.76	2.06	6.38
2018-06-28	4.17	21.87	3.1	21.51	3.42	21.31	3.64	21.37	817	-5	481	5.44	24.62	6.93	29.91	1.03	52.13
2018-06-30	4.2	22.13	2.7	23.49	3.42	22.33	3.64	22.2	761	-4.5	456	5.44	23.9	5.95	25.58	-4.27	416
2018-07-02	4.22	15.64	2.8	4.49	3.28	8.22	3.51	10.06	397	3.95	13.55	2.05	5.68	2.31	4.34	2.45	3.9
2018-07-03	4.24	24.11	2.7	12.88	3.28	17.4	3.51	19.1	1740	148	99.95	1.4	12.22	-0.55	43.61	-3.68	149
2018-07-15	4.39	20.72	3	11.59	3.28	13.48	3.51	15.05	644	-10.75	2832	2.46	11.61	2.12	14.17	2.93	11.17
2018-09-01	4.12	14.21	2.9	6.44	3.1	7.15	3.67	10.69	926	-24	347836	2.23	7.55	-1.45	68.56	3.6	10.17
2018-09-25	3.9	16.75	2.6	5.4	3.1	9.51	3.67	14.65	345	2	5.78	2.23	4.46	2.7	6.1	2.44	4.54
2018-09-29	3.84	16.8	2.6	5.54	3.1	9.5	3.67	15.13	389	0.38	28.98	2.23	4.7	3.76	16	3.56	14.06
2018-10-09	3.7	17.17	2.4	5.74	3.02	10.92	3.25	13	394	-0.68	58.34	3.66	16.83	0.62	28.53	-0.87	63.51
2018-11-13	3.46	27.25	2.9	20.69	2.88	20.48	2.7	18.61	559	5.55	47.55	1.71	15.95	2.99	21.67	2.96	21.34

D FORECASTING

Using the `pvl` functions to forecast the GHI in energy yield estimations requires a valid T_L to be used (see appendix C. A library value of T_L is a starting point, but that will be relevant for the day it was measured on and so may not be accurate for the forecast day, leading to bias. A short term (same day) or very short term (e.g. hourly ahead) forecast can be made by calculating the T_L by measurements the same day (e.g. using the day, or the preceding hour).

D.1 Short Timescale

In Fig. 19 are plotted the cumulative number of change points n_{cp} for the two days in Fig 15 for each hour starting at sunrise and continuing through to sunset. From Fig. 6 we know to expect the rate of n_{cp} to increase from sunrise, reach a maximum mid-morning, begin to drop through noon, to rise and peak again mid-afternoon, then drop up to sunset. This gives rise to the distinctive bend in the curves of the modelled clear sky n_{cp} . When adding the n_{cp}^{obs} from these days a bendy line is also apparent, which either matches or deviates from the clear sky model based on the level of intermittency experienced in that day. For 2018-07-02 there is only a small amount of intermittency and the GHI does not go beyond the range expected between a `cda` and an urban smog. The measured points match well to the model s-curve, though even the small amount of present intermittency (particularly centred around noon) does serve to bias the fit toward lower T_L , adjusting the significance threshold σ can tune the sensitivity of this fit. On the next day, 2018-07-03, however, there is significant intermittency in the first half of the day due to a small level of cloud on this otherwise clear day. This builds a significant bias in to the cumulative n_{cp} distribution which causes a full day T_L fit to fail.

Figure 19

Even though the full day fit to 2018-07-03 fails, we see that once the sky is clear the cumulative n_{cp} follows its expected form, albeit offset from where it needs to be. Adjusting to fit shorter segments of the day allows us to reduce the chances of encountering intermittency that may only be present for part of a day, starting from sunrise and increasing to 1, 2, or 3 h after enables us to make a prediction of the yield on that day (assuming the weather stays clear). In Fig. 20 are plotted the $\text{kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$ residuals between measurement and model for 2018 *clear* dataset, where the T_L BB fit has been made with $\sigma = 5 \text{ W/m}^2$, these fall within the overestimate of the insolation from `cda` and underestimate from default `pvl` models most of the time. The days are indexed in order of increasing number of change points in the 3h post sunrise dataset showing that it is the days with the highest level of intermittency in the morning that are most detrimental to the overall forecast improvement. In general the overall bias (accuracy) is good, and so is the precision for 15/20 days. So, in aggregate it may be okay as a forecasting method, but for any individual day the predicted insolation is very far from guaranteed. In Fig. 21 the MAPE is plotted with days arranged in date order for comparison with `PVGIS`, `pvl`, `Meteonorm` and `Aeronet` derived T_L values for the days, with the shaded region demarcating the range of prediction errors between the different

fit periods. In general the improvement in fit compared to `pvlib` defaults is apparent, and generally in agreement to the PVGIS measurements, with the advantage they are being made in advance and not after the fact as the PVGIS values would be.

Figure 20: The residuals (observed - modelled) insolation for each of the 2018, *clear* days, with T_L fits made using measurements up to 3 h from sunrise arranged in increasing order of n_{cp} in the 3 h dataset.

Figure 21: As Fig. 20, but for MAPE and adding comparisons to PVGIS, Meteonorm and Aeronet derived T_L .

D.2 Very Short Timescale

The days for which there is significant intermittency in the early morning may spoil forecast on those days, but we have seen from 2013-07-03 that a day may not be intermittent all the time. By moving the forecast window such that the T_L fit for the preceding hour's measurements can forecast the next hour's insolation can any further improvements be made? Here we run into an issue because at local noon when the Sun is culminating in the sky there is very little deterministic variation in the solar resource, i.e. there are no expected change points to fit on. This can be seen in the left plot of Fig. 22, in the 1st period an hour after sunrise there is a clear trend of n_{cp} with T_L , but by noon (period 4 at the winter solstice, period at the summer solstice) there is no usable differentiation between clear sky models at all. This is borne out in the right plot of Fig. 22 where the SSR worsens up to period 4 and only improves again in the afternoon once the rate of change of n_{cp} picks up again as the sunlight traverses larger airmasses once again. Unfortunately this will

be after much of the electricity has already been generated, thereby making a forecast largely moot. Histogramming the SSR in Fig 23 for three of the periods during the day shows that intermittency generally introduced at noon compounds the decline in the forecast and is not really aided by moving to higher thresholds to compensate, indeed the loss in number of n_{cp} serves to make it harder to produce a viable fit in these short periods.

Figure 22: . Left: The Linke turbidity factor (T_L) expected for a given number of change points (n_{cp}) for different times of day and day of year. Plotted are the values for the winter (blue/yellow) and summer (green/red) solstice. Period 1 is the hour after sunrise (dash-dot), period 4 (dash-dot-dot-dot-dot) and period 9 (dash-dot-dot-dot-dot) encompass noon for winter and summer respectively. Right: The sum of square residuals (SSR) for (measured - fit) residuals in the respective fit periods in 2018 where a valid fit could be found between n_{cp} and T_L for two different significance thresholds (blue solid line, $\sigma = 5 \text{ W/m}^2$; yellow dashed line, $\sigma = 25 \text{ W/m}^2$; green dotted line, $\sigma = 50 \text{ W/m}^2$).

Figure 23: The sum of square residuals (SSR) for 2018 in various periods Top panels for $\sigma = 5$, bottom panels for $\sigma = 25$. Default here refers to the default `pvl` T_L for a day; forecast refers to the T_L calculated for pyranometer measurement change points in the preceding period.

There are a total of 4279 1 h daylight periods in 2018, 364 of which will be the hour after sunrise therefore no prior hour forecast is possible for them, making for a total of 3915 possible forecast periods. Of those 1885(2234) had predictions from valid fits ($T_L > 0$) in the prior hour for $\sigma=5(25)$ respectively (i.e. increasing the threshold does help increase the chance of smoothing the fluctuations down to get a forecast, but increasing it too much will then make it sensitive to suffering small number fluctuations in n_{cp}). Of those only 931(1296) [24/33%] were able to provide a fit better than default cda, mostly due to the noon time issue of lack of difference in n_{cp} between different T_L models.

E COMPARISON TO OTHER METHODS

Many methods have been developed for examining variability in the solar resource [19, 17] and even more exist for investigating time series in general. Here we look at two popular methods for examining time series and see how Bayesian blocks compares.

E.1 Variability Index

The Variability Index (VI) [19] is calculated as

$$VI = \frac{\sum_{k=2}^n \sqrt{(G^{\text{obs}}_k - G^{\text{obs}}_{k-1})^2 + \Delta t^2}}{\sum_{k=2}^n \sqrt{(G^{\text{sim}}_k - G^{\text{sim}}_{k-1})^2 + \Delta t^2}} \quad (10)$$

where G^{obs} is the k th measured irradiance of in a series of length n , G^{sim} is the expectation from clear sky model, and Δt the time between measurements. In Fig. 24 we see a good correlation between VI and BB n_{cp} for both GHI and DHI, with perhaps a little more sensitivity of BB to intermittency, at least on these 1 s measurement timescales. There is the addition that a BB comes with a timing measurement on the change point as to when changes in behaviour are occurring for readily identifying periods of increased intermittency.

Figure 24: The correlation of Variability Index (VI) with Bayesian blocks n_{cp} (BB) as calculated for Loughborough pyranometer for each day of 2018. The dotted line is to guide the eye for an ideal correlation and not a fit to the data. Data marked according to weather CI classification: *clear* (\blacktriangledown), *mixed* (\times), *overcast* (\blacksquare). Left: GHI Right: DHI

E.2 Lomb-Scargle Periodogram

A Lomb-Scargle periodogram is effectively a Fourier transform (FT) of the measurement points, with the advantage that it is slightly more forgiving of data gaps than a strict FT would be. In Fig. 25 the Lomb-Scargle periodograms identifies the longer timescale diurnal peaks of the dataset, to which the BB analysis will be blind, but the higher frequency characteristic scales identified by the BB approach are lost in the periodogram white noise.

Figure 25: Lomb-Scargle periodograms as calculated for Loughborough pyranometer for each day of 2018. Data divided according to clear (blue)/mixed (green)/overcast (red) conditions. Guides to the eye are given by the black lines at 5 s, 10 s, 30 s, 60 s, 5 min, 7.5 min, 15 min; and by the grey lines at each hour between 1-24 h.

F IRRADIANCE

F.1 Global Horizontal Irradiance

Figure 26: Global Horizontal Irradiance displayed according to CI weather classification. The cyan and gold dashed lines represent the peak GHI at local noon each day according to clear and dry atmosphere and default turbidity conditions respectively.

F.2 Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance

Figure 27: Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance displayed according to CI weather classification. The cyan and gold dashed lines represent the peak GHI at local noon each day according to clear and dry atmosphere and default turbidity conditions respectively.

G SEASONAL VARIATION

As we see in Fig. 1 the solar resource is expected to vary through the year, being maximal at the summer solstice and minimal at the winter solstice. Since longer days give more daylight resulting more opportunity for intermittent behaviour to be observed it is perhaps not surprising that in Fig. 28 we tend to see a similar trend for greater variability in solar resource to be measured in the summer than in winter for both VI and BB methods. Periods of *clear* weather do see significant drops in both metrics, down to clear sky model simulation values, but even that has a similar seasonal trend due to length of day differences.

Figure 28: Variability Index (VI, blue solid line, y-axis) and Bayesian blocks change points (CP) as calculated for Loughborough pyranometer (orange dashed line, y2-axis) and pvlib simulation (cyan, dash-dot line, y2-axis) for each day of 2018. Top: GHI Bottom: DHI